

Design of Multivalent Fluorescent Dendritic Probes for Site-Specific Labeling of Biomolecules

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INTRODUCTION

Over the last decade, fluorescent labeling of biomolecules has become a powerful tool for bioimaging and diagnostics. In contrast to radioisotopes, fluorescent dyes have the advantage of being of low cost, ease of disposal, and the versatility of multicolor labeling.¹ While promising, there is a major drawback accompanying fluorescent labeling *i.e.* inherently low sensitivity.² To overcome this issue and expand the applicability of fluorescent probes, it is apparent that dyes with strong fluorescence signal need to be identified, synthesized and conjugated to biomolecules without jeopardizing the biological activity of the final construct. As a mean to enhance the fluorescence signal, different approaches have been suggested including conjugation of multiple fluorescent dyes to the biomolecules. Unfortunately, an obvious disadvantage of this approach is the high number of involved functionalization sites that may affect the specificity of conjugated

biomolecule.^{2,3} A natural strategy to circumvent such concern is the use of orthogonal linkers with the capacity to carry multiple copies of fluorescent dyes as well as a single selective reactive group for site-specific conjugation to the biomolecule. However, a limitation coupled to this approach relates to the high dye content per macromolecule that can reduce fluorescence signal due to various processes such as self-quenching of fluorescence.²⁻⁶ Interestingly, although rare, some studies have described a stronger fluorescence with the inclusion of multiple fluorescent units.² Consequently, the development of a set of intrinsically similar structures, sharing the same functional group for chemoselective bioligation and bearing different concentration of fluorescent units, would provide the appropriate conditions for accurate structure-to-property assessment with emphasis on site-specific labeling and improved fluorescence signals.

In this context, dendrons, as highly branched and monodisperse wedge-shaped scaffolds with multiple peripheral end-groups and a single reactive functionality at the focal point, bring the option of orthogonal reactions^{7,8} suited for site-specific labeling of biomolecules.^{2,9} For instance, Wängler *et al.*² synthesized a library of polyamidoamine (PAMAM) dendrons being peripherally decorated with various fluorescent dyes and encompassing a single thiol functionality at the focal point. In their work and for most of fluorescently labeled dendrons, the fluorescence signal decreased with increased number of dye units, and only dansylated dendrons met the requirements of enhanced fluorescence signals.

Independent of conjugation chemistry or orthogonal linkers, cyanine-based dyes are one of the most promising Near Infrared (NIR) dyes, ideal for *in vivo* and *in vitro* optical imaging.¹⁰ Among them, Cy5 has been identified as the champion as it can be excited at wavelength above 600 nm *i.e.* where the auto-fluorescence background of live cells is lower by orders of magnitude as compared with the excitation range of TMR, Cy3, and Cy3.5.⁴ Moreover, scanners in microarray systems have the capacity for signal detection of Cy5. Most examples in literature detail the monovalent conjugation of Cy5 probes using simple bifunctional linkers.¹¹⁻¹⁷ Dendrimers functionalized with Cy5 substituents, either at periphery¹⁸⁻²⁰ or at focal point,^{8,20,21} have also been reported on as monodisperse scaffolds, including popular PAMAM¹⁸ or 2,2-bis(methylol)propionic acid (bis-MPA)²¹ architecture among others. The bioconjugation of Cy5 *via* covalent linkages to the target molecule often involves click chemistries^{11,14,16,19} although 1, 2-addition reaction¹², or reaction with amines through NHS chemistry¹⁷ have also been described. Of note is the use of hydrazide¹³ or hydrazine¹⁵ monovalent Cy5 probes, since they react selectively with carbohydrate on the Fc region of antibodies, with a well-defined stoichiometry of

conjugation, without affecting the binding site of the biomolecule.

From the great number of dendritic scaffolds available, orthogonally functionalized dendrons based on bis-MPA belong to the most desirable scaffolds for biomedical applications. This is mainly due their biodegradable and biocompatible profile, facile synthesis, proven flawless nature as well as the large and exact number of functional groups with orthogonal features.²²

Herein, we propose the synthesis of a set of novel probes displaying mono or multivalent hydrazine/dye functionalities. The multivalent features capitalizes on dendrons based on bis-MPA as sophisticated orthogonal linkers with amplifying capacity, Figure 1. Dendrons of generation 1 (G1) and G3 were synthesized and peripherally decorated with an exact number of Cy5 fluorescent moieties and comprised a single hydrazine functionality at the focal point. As a proof-of-concept, the fluorescence of these multivalent dendrons was evaluated and compared with the monovalent Cy5 (G0), as well as their suitability for antibody labeling. To our knowledge, no bis-MPA based fluorescent dendritic probe for chemoselective labeling of biomolecules has been reported and it is envisaged to highlight their use in fluorescence signal amplification applications, such as bioimaging or immunoassays.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To explore bis-MPA based frameworks as versatile fluorescent amplifiers for enhanced detection of biomolecules we sought out a novel synthetic scheme. The dendrons targeted should display (i) a single hydrazine functionality in the focal point, for chemoselective reaction with carbonyl from aldehydes present on the biomolecules; (ii) a tetraethyleneglycol extender that provides spacious distance between the hydrazine group and the main dendritic skeleton *i.e.* to avoid steric hindrance during bioconjugation and promote solubility in aqueous media; and (iii)

multiple fluorescent Cy5 moieties at the periphery, for signal amplification. As seen in Figure 1, a set of fluorescent dendrons (**G0-Cy5**, **G1-Cy5** and **G3-Cy5**) were synthesized prior to their bioconjugation to immunoglobulin as a model biomolecule.

Initially, the precursors were constructed to exhibit the appropriate orthogonal functionalities *i.e.* protected hydrazine in the focal point and alkyne groups in the periphery, for further dye functionalization via click chemistry. A more in-depth description of the synthetic strategy is shown in Scheme 1A. First, Boc-hydrazine-TEG-OH **4** was synthesized in four consecutive reaction steps. The synthesis was initiated by the derivatization of tetraethyleneglycol (TEG) as benzyl protected TEG (**1**).⁷ Then after, a succinic moiety was incorporated to yield the carboxylic acid functional **2** that facilitated covalent coupling of amino-protected diboc-2-hydroxyethylhydrazine, *via* fluoride promoted esterification (FPE) chemistry²³ resulting in **3**. The benzyl group was deprotected using catalytic hydrogenation resulting in the Boc-hydrazine-TEG-OH **4** (Figure S1) with an average yield of 85%. To generate the mono and multivalent hydrazine/dye probes, **4** was used as a precursor. In one end, the 4-pentynoic acid was covalently attached *via* FPE chemistry which yielded **5** in a quantitative yield. This represents the G0 dendron with protected hydrazine and bearing one alkyne group, ready for click functionalization, Scheme 1B and Figure S2. In the other end, the use of growth/activation divergent growth approach resulted in dendrons G1 **9** and G3 **15** displaying two and eight peripheral alkyne groups, respectively. In both cases, the dendritic frameworks were isolated in an average yield of 80%, Scheme 1C-D and Figures S5, S7-8. In contrast to the G1 **9**, the G3 **15** was synthesized as previously reported⁷ prior to the deprotection by palladium-catalyzed hydrogenation, introduction of succinic modified diboc-2-hydroxyethylhydrazine and finally the functionalization with peripheral

alkynes. The synthesis of the three alkyne decorated molecules (**5**, **9** and **15**) and their intermediates were monitored by MALDI-TOF MS (Figure 2A), purified by extractions and characterized by ¹H and ¹³C-NMR.

For the introduction of fluorescence to the orthogonally functionalized probes, Sulfo-Cyanine 5 azide (sulfo-Cy5-azide) was chosen. This due to its (i) excitation maximum at 646 nm, which makes it suitable for microarray scanner systems; (ii) azide functionality that allows for coupling to **5**, **9** and **15** via Copper catalyzed Azide-Alkyne Cycloaddition (CuAAC) and (iii) additional sulfo-groups that facilitate water solubility and decrease aggregation of dye molecules in heavily labeled conjugates.²⁴ For the introduction of fluorescent Cy5, the click reaction was optimized for the monovalent molecule **5**. Traditional CuAAC using CuSO₄/sodium ascorbate in THF/H₂O (1:1) at 50°C was first performed. The reaction was monitored by MALDI-TOF MS until completion and the di-Boc-hydrazine monovalent sulfo-Cy5 **6** was isolated in quantitative yields by preparative TLC using EtOAc/MeOH (1:1). Interestingly, the click reaction was found to proceed at much higher rate when performed in DMSO using CuBr/PMDTA as catalyst pair, at room temperature and under argon as inert atmosphere. This is reasoned to be an effect of solubility in which the starting materials were soluble in DMSO in contrast to THF/H₂O mixture. Utilizing the CuAAC with CuBr/PMDTA as catalyst pair and DMSO as solvent were chosen for the synthesis of **10**, a di-Boc-hydrazine TEG core decorated with two sulfo-Cy5 groups. The reaction was complete after overnight stirring and dialyzed against water to obtain **10** as a pure compound with a yield of 88%. For the G3-Cy5 **16** with eight peripheral copies of sulfo-Cy5, CuAAC in THF/H₂O (1:1). To reach completion, the reaction required 48 hours of stirring at elevated temperature (50°C). After solvents elimination, the crude mixture was dissolved in water and purified by means of sephadex G-25 to exclude excess of dye, affording dendron **16** with 57% yield. For all

probes decorated with sulfo-Cy5, the reactions were considered completed upon the disappearance of alkyne-derived molecules (**5**, **9** and **15**, respectively) in the MALDI-TOF-MS and their purity corroborated by NMR (Figures S4, S6 and S9). For example, Figure 2B details spectra of **6**, which support the complete consumption of the alkyne group (absence of the signal at 2.25 ppm) along with the formation of triazol ring with specific signal allocated at 7.84 ppm. The click reaction is also exemplified by the shift of signals belonging to methylene groups next to the azide in sulfo-Cy5-azide from 1.44 and 1.79 ppm to 4.39 and 2.75 ppm in **6**, and signal displacement of methylene group directly bounded to alkyne from 2.47 ppm in **5**, to 3.02 ppm in **6** (Figures S3, S4). MALDI-TOF spectra also confirmed the structure of **6** (Figure S10).

The final activation of these probes included the deprotection of the hydrazine groups. For the monovalent sulfo-Cy5 **6** and divalent sulfo-Cy5 **10**, the deprotection was accomplished using TFA/DCM (1:1) at room temperature, affording **G0-Cy5** and **G1-Cy5** in quantitative yields. As can be seen in Figures S11, the MALDI-TOF MS for the **G0-Cy5** revealed a molecular weight corresponding to expected ionized mass of 1178 (M+Na). The deprotection of the octavalent sulfo-Cy5 **16** was carried out in pure TFA. This is due to solubility issues in TFA/DCM (1:1) governed by the higher amount of water soluble dyes at the periphery. The **G3-Cy5** was successfully isolated in a quantitative yield. In all cases, the deprotection of the Boc groups was confirmed by ¹H-NMR (Figures S4, S6 and S9) and resulted in fluorescently labeled probes **G0-Cy5**, **G1-Cy5** and **G3-Cy5** bearing 1, 2 or 8 dye moieties and a single hydrazine ready for biomolecule labeling (Figure 1).

Satisfied with the successful synthetic machinery of the probes, their performance was evaluated by UV and fluorescence spectroscopic techniques, measuring $3.8 \cdot 10^{-7}$ M solutions in 0.01 M Na₃PO₄, 0.15 M NaCl, pH 7.0 for each dendron. As shown in Figure 2C, UV

spectra revealed an increase in absorbance at 646 nm along with the number of dyes. The molar extinction coefficient, ϵ_{646} , was 80342, 154050 and 600459 M⁻¹·cm⁻¹ for **G0-Cy5**, **G1-Cy5** and **G3-Cy5**, respectively. A ϵ_{646} ratio of 1/1.9/7.5 was obtained for the probes. These values are in close approximation to the number of fluorescent sulfo-Cy5 units available on each dendron *i.e.* 1:2:8, confirming the peripheral valence as well as the success of fluorescent decoration.

Concerning the fluorescence of the dendrons, results shown in Figure 2D, an increased number of fluorescent units yields higher fluorescence emission for the dendrons (**G3-Cy5** > **G1-Cy5** > **G0-Cy5**). Quantum yields (ϕ) obtained for **G0-Cy5**, **G1-Cy5** and **G3-Cy5** were noted to 0.33, 0.22 and 0.21, respectively. It should be noted that molecules with high quantum yield and extinction coefficient have the brightest features. To compare the brightness of different fluorophores, the relative brightness of fluorophore is taken by multiplying the extinction coefficient with the quantum yield ($\epsilon \cdot \phi$).²⁵ Brightness obtained for **G0-Cy5**, **G1-Cy5** and **G3-Cy5** were 26330, 34046 and 128374, respectively. High brightness is required to obtain strong fluorescence signal. Although ϕ for **G3-Cy5** is the lowest, it shows the highest brightness. Therefore, the **G1-Cy5** and **G3-Cy5** dendrons decorated with 2 or 8 Cy5 dyes, were considered to fulfill the prerequisites for enhance fluorescence signals when compared to the monovalent **G0-Cy5**. These results demonstrate the sought proof-of-concept, contradicting earlier reports on decrease in fluorescence for dendrimers decorated with high number of dyes.^{2,5,6}

The fact that fluorescence intensity of dendrimers decreases with increasing number of coupled dyes can be attributed to the self-quenching, consequence of the relatively small Stokes shift of the dyes and their proximity within the molecule.² In the precedent study, only compounds derivatized with dansyl chloride have shown to enhance fluorescence

signals, showing relatively low self-quenching due to large Stokes shift (195 nm).² Our Cy5 decorated dendrimers also present increased fluorescence with high number of dyes despite the low Stokes shift of sulfo-Cy5 (16 nm). This could be explained by the presence of additional sulfo groups, which increases the hydrophilicity of the dendrimer's periphery and its solubility in water, avoiding aggregation and reducing closeness of dye moieties.

As the main motivation for the construction of these probes was their applicability in biomolecule labeling for bioimaging or diagnostic, we further assessed their site-specific conjugation to α -Human IgG Fc as a model antibody. The methodology used for labeling capitalized on site-directed conjugation to the aldehydes being generated through oxidation process of 1,2-diols in sialic acids. These are displayed at glycan carbohydrate chains attached to the CH2 domain between the heavy chains in the Fc region.²⁶ The aldehydes carbonyls were envisaged to selectively react with hydrazine groups to generate hydrazone linkages without compromising antibody activity, recognition or causing further oxidative damage. The protocol²⁷ utilized was based on a mild oxidation of polysaccharide chains with NaIO₄ and the subsequent conjugation with the set of fluorescent probes **G0-Cy5**, **G1-Cy5** and **G3-Cy5**, Figure 3A. Upon labeling, a purification step using Sephadex-G-25 was necessary to exclude any unconjugated fluorescent probes. Dialysis filtration was also performed as an additional purification step to ensure the exclusion of any remaining probes. As visualized in Figure 3A and for the purified antibodies, a clear shift in blue color intensity can be observed, which reflects the amplification capacity the fluorescent dendrons provides to the final biomolecules.

Sodium dodecyl sulfate polyacrilamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) analysis was performed to confirm the covalent attachment of the probes to the antibody, Figure 3B. The use of Commassie staining as a detection

technique enabled the semi-quantification of the labeled antibody. By the comparison to unlabeled counterparts, as controls, it was confirmed that similar recovery could be obtained for all three fluorescently conjugated biomolecules. The fluorescent detection revealed bands for labeled antibodies while the controls were undetectable. This corroborates on successful covalent attachment of the fluorescent probes to the antibody via hydrazone linkages, Figure 3B.

Absorbance and fluorescence of the labeled antibodies were registered using $1 \cdot 10^{-6}$ M solutions in 0.01 M Na₃PO₄, 0.15 M NaCl, pH 7.0. The absorbance registered a band at 646 nm. Higher intensity was noted with increasing number of dye units present on the fluorescent probes, *i.e.* ϵ_{646} values of 49667, 274985 and 2280894 M⁻¹·cm⁻¹ for **IgG-G0-Cy5**, **IgG-G1-Cy5** and **IgG-G3-Cy5**, respectively (Figure 3C left). Interestingly, the spectra for **IgG-G3-Cy5** had a pronounced bimodal shape with a maximum intensity at 600 nm. Such behavior has been previously observed by Gruber *et al.*⁴ for IgG labeled with six Cy5 molecules. In their work, it was postulated to be an effect of H aggregates formation, so called H-dimers. This was explained by the tendency of cyanine dyes to aggregate in solution through plane-to-plane stacking (parallel aggregates) or through an end-to-end arrangement (head-to-tail). The transition to the upper state in parallel aggregates leads to a hypsochromic (red) shift and these groups of molecules are called H aggregates.²⁰

As seen in Figure 3D, the fluorescence properties of labeled antibodies noted the maximum emission for **IgG-G1-Cy5** ($\phi = 0.25$, $\epsilon \cdot \phi = 67891$) followed by **IgG-G0-Cy5** ($\phi = 0.41$; $\epsilon \cdot \phi = 20473$). The antibody labeled with **G1-Cy5** probe, compared to the conjugation with **G0-Cy5**, enhanced the fluorescence emission by one degree of magnitude. Surprisingly, **IgG-G3-Cy5** was barely fluorescent with an extremely low ϕ value of 0.02. A plausible explanation is that most of the photon are absorbed and

deactivated by means of non-radiative process. The drop in fluorescence of **IgG-G3-Cy5** compared to the neat **G3-Cy5** could be explained by the more restricted environment where the dendron is confined in the IgG, probably hydrophobic, leading to a more rigid conformation and thereof to a higher proximity among Cy5 units. H-dimer formation was previously reported for Cy5,^{20,28} and other dyes^{28,29} as the cause of quenching for cases with a high degree of labeling. To investigate whether the scarce fluorescent properties of **IgG-G3-Cy5** is due to this phenomena, absorbance and fluorescence values with and without sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) were compared.^{4,28,29} The addition of SDS to **IgG-G3-Cy5** was found to decrease the intensity of the band absorbance at 600 nm while increasing that at 646 nm (Figure 3C right) as well as the increase in intensity for the band in the fluorescence spectrum (Figure 3D right). The large reversed anomalous effect could be explained by the partial unfolding of the antibody because of disruption of the tertiary structure due to SDS. In spite of the formation of Cy5 dimers, the quenching of Cy5 fluorescence in the highly Cy5-labeled biomolecule may be due to resonance energy transfer.⁴ Similar argument can explain the observed fluorescent band for **IgG-G3-Cy5** after SDS-PAGE, since SDS and β -mercaptoethanol used in denaturalization step may affect protein conformation, being the dendritic structure surrounded by a less restricted environment, which would reduce quenching.

From the three conjugates studied, the **IgG-G1-Cy5** functionalized with dendrons bearing two dyes moieties was found to be the most fluorescent. These findings are in good agreement with previous studies of the monovalent-Cy5/protein ratios in which 2 to 3 Cy5 labels per antibody resulted in optimal fluorescence.^{4,30} However, these studies employed monovalent NHS-activated-dyes as a random-site bioconjugation to present lysines on the biomolecules. In this context, the orthogonality present in hydrazine/click

frameworks provides water-soluble probes with site-directed conjugation and detection without jeopardizing the recognition site of the antibody.

EXPERIMENTAL

See Supporting Information for full experimental data, including ¹H and ¹³C NMR and MALDI-TOF results as well as details for materials and analytical techniques.

CONCLUSIONS

Due to the increasing use of fluorescent probes in biomedical applications, the development of novel fluorescent probes that allows for chemoselective labeling of biomolecules is highly desirable. In here, we describe the synthetic design of dendritic scaffolds based bis-MPA as a monomer displaying a protected hydrazine and multiple alkyne functionalities. Three scaffolds (**5**, **9** and **15**), with orthogonal features were, for the first time, successfully decorated with the highly desirable bioimaging dye sulfo-Cy5, bearing one, two or eight fluorescent copies along with a single reactive hydrazine. The potential of the multivalent hydrazine/dyes probes, as a conjugation reagent to functionalize biomolecules, was demonstrated on α -Human IgG Fc. The most favorable signal amplification was obtained for immunoglobulin labeled with **G1-Cy5** bearing 2 units of sulfo-Cy5. It was found to enhance the fluorescence by one order of magnitude when compared to the monovalent probe **G0-Cy5**. This makes hydrazine functionalized **G1-Cy5** dendron a valuable candidate for macromolecules labeling for applications such as immunoassays signal amplification. In contrast, strong fluorescence quenching was observed for α -Human IgG Fc labeled with **G3-Cy5**. While not favorable in this study, such quenching phenomena may be suppressed by the conjugation of the probe to biomolecules with less restricted environment. This could facilitate the exploitation of **G3-Cy5** as a strong fluorescent enhancer for bioimaging and diagnostic applications. Finally, the chemistry is

not limited to Cy5 and alternative dyes may lead to higher fluorescent emission for biomolecules labeled with dendron utilizing the presented synthetic strategy.

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FIGURE 1. Mono and multivalent hydrazine/dyes probes consisting of hydrazine functionalization as linking group, a hydrophilic TEG spacer and one or multiple units of fluorescent.

SCHEME 1. Synthesis of fluorescent dendrimers. A) Spacer synthesis based on derivatization of a TEG chain with a diboc-protected hydrazine containing molecule. B) Synthesis of **G0-Cy5** bearing one fluorescent moiety. C) Synthesis of dendron **G1-Cy5** bearing two fluorescent moieties. D) Synthesis of dendron **G3-Cy5** bearing eight fluorescent moieties.

FIGURE 2. Characterization of dendrons. A) From left to right, MALDI-TOF monitoring of alkyne decorated dendrons synthesis. B) $^1\text{H-NMR}$ characterization of **G0-Cy5**. C) UV-visible spectroscopy of dendrons **G0-Cy5**, **G1-Cy5** and **G3-Cy5** measured at $3.8 \cdot 10^{-7}$ M in 0.01 M Na_3PO_4 , 0.15 M NaCl , pH 7.0. D) Fluorescence emission of dendrons **G0-Cy5**, **G1-Cy5** and **G3-Cy5** measured at $3.8 \cdot 10^{-7}$ M in 0.01 M Na_3PO_4 , 0.15 M NaCl , pH 7.0.

FIGURE 3. Antibody labeling and characterization. A) Antibody labeling scheme. B) SDS-PAGE characterization of labeled antibody. A molecular weight marker (lane 1), four decreasing amounts of unlabeled IgG as control (lanes 2-5) and conjugates **IgG-G0-Cy5**, **IgG-G1-Cy5**, **IgG-G3-Cy5** (lanes 6-8) were loaded. Commassie (top) and fluorescent detection (bottom). C) Absorbance spectra obtained for antibody labeled with the series of synthesized dendrons (**IgG-G0-Cy5**, **IgG-G1-Cy5**, **IgG-G3-Cy5**) measured at $1 \cdot 10^{-6}$ M in 0.01 M Na_3PO_4 , 0.15 M NaCl, pH 7.0 (left). Comparison of the different shape obtained for **IgG-G3-Cy5** (middle). Change in absorbance after 90 min of adding SDS (1%) to **IgG-G3-Cy5** solution. D) Fluorescence emission results obtained for labeled IgG (**IgG-G0-Cy5**, **IgG-G1-Cy5**, **IgG-G3-Cy5**) measured at $1 \cdot 10^{-6}$ M in 0.01 M Na_3PO_4 , 0.15 M NaCl, pH 7.0 (left) and change in fluorescence 90 min after adding SDS (1%) (right).